

An analysis on the interrelationship regarding digital technology and politics

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On an unassuming spring of 1989¹, British scientist Tim Berners-Lee inaugurated a revolutionary epoch when he constructed history's first online-infrastructure system at CERN, in Switzerland. This wide-area-network would eventually creep into the common people's internet of today, collectively and immeasurably altering our lives. One such altered area was politics, which had walked hand-in-hand alongside this revolution, transitioning as people began interacting differently in-light of the newfound global amalgamation, with many believing the internet had propitiously elucidated the many damning quandaries of politics; now, supposedly, existed an instantaneous news-source, a new-found digital public sphere, and an important public utility for free-speech, all for the people to converse the fortuities of current affairs. Yet, this purportedly stupefying infrastructure has only since proven its bona-feid nature; simply a modern-day trojan horse, dramatically mortifying foundations of political values through its propagation of damning social inequalities and partisan lethargy, all whilst apportioning the ability to influence ideological rhetorics into the nonpareil elite, collectively posing the consequential question: has digital technology really altered politics beneficially?

From a wider lens, users within the internet symbolise the 'digital sphere'; which German philosopher Jürgen Habermas construes as "realms of social life wherein

¹ Cailliau, Robert. n.d. *A short history of the Web*. CERN. Accessed January 5, 2025.

<https://home.cern/science/computing/birth-web/short-history-web>.

public opinion can be formed"². This 'public-utility' is claimed to have positively shaped an autonomous public symposium toward politics, with American writer Harold Rheingold arguing that the digital sphere provides 'large social groups to govern themselves without dictators' in a form of freedom-of-speech³. Coupled with the internet's ability to disperse information at increased rates, there is immense assumption regarding the digital-sphere's contribution toward enlivening political interest. However, these assumptions remain as such; The predicaments introduced since advents within digital-technology have only held politics back immeasurably, causing both common-people and politicians to bear this brunt.

This failure is evident within digital news, which some mistakenly claim has positively increased diverse ideological representation within presenting information, explaining their overwhelming consumer-centric rise: A 2019 Pew Centre study saw 20% of Americans garnering news online⁴, with 2022 academic

² Habermas, Jurgen. 1989. *The structural transformation of the public sphere : an inquiry into a category of bourgeois society*. Translated by Thomas Burger. N.p.: MIT Press.

³ Rheingold, Harold. 2000. *The Virtual Community*. N.p.: MIT Press.

⁴ Rosenberg, Stacy, and Stacy Rosenberg. 2024. *Nearly as Many Americans Prefer to Get Their Local News Online as Prefer the TV Set*. Pew Research Center. August 8, 2024.

<https://www.pewresearch.org/journalism/2019/03/26/nearly-as-many-americans-prefer-to-get-their-local-news-online-as-prefer-the-tv-set/>

studies witnessing nearly 60% utilise this source for gun-legislation news⁵. The truth, however, is that digital technologies have simply propagated ‘instantaneous journalism’; a modern-day goldrush whereby writers churn out information post-haste, on-the-second, with cacophonous reporting being the norm.

Unnecessarily minute transgressions within the politico-sphere have become amplified, undermining the much-needed scrutiny on larger issues, and eroding the cornerstone of former journalistic integrity. One such instance was in 2024, when British Science Secretary Michelle Donelan faced criticism after scrutinising academics for sharing extremist views online, leading into legal action and a £15,000 settlement, whereby the media overshadowed discussions on her department's research policies, instead choosing sensationalism. This unfortunate shift of focus has been also prominent long-term, with former Alaskan Governor Sarah Palin, who ran for Vice-Presidency in 2008, facing immense media backlash regarding her daughter’s premarital pregnancy, undermining true analysis over her policy commitments as VP. Both are simply of the many instances whereby digital-news solely prioritises instantaneous sensationalism over policy critique, a highly-threatening aspect of digital technology which forces the hand of politicians to become ‘theatre-actors’ for the people rather than attend to their needs, eroding value within journalism and politics as a result of technological influence within both.

⁵ South EC, Hemenway D, Webster DW. *Gun violence research is surging to inform solutions to a devastating public health crisis*. *Prev Med*. 2022 Dec;165(Pt A):107325. doi: 10.1016/j.ypmed.2022.107325. Epub 2022 Oct 27. PMID: 36374716; PMCID: PMC9642971.

It is mistakenly believed that traditional discussions of politics have failed at inclusivity, whereby feminist scholar Nancy Fraser argued that real-life conversation has historically disadvantaged vulnerable communities, including persons-of-color, disabled and the LGBTQ⁶, with other scholars contending the digital-sphere to have provided safer communities for said personages. Despite a seemingly logical thought process, online political spaces have simply proliferated unethical exclusion, given their inherent quick-paced nature, whereby portrayals of people's offline identities within profile pictures/banners have simply made discriminating easier and rampant, with a 2023 Nottingham Trent study discovering that online contributions from black individuals were instinctively perceived as less credible⁷, oppositionary to other racial backgrounds. This concept of digital exclusion is also prominent within politically-tailored forums, whereby researcher Steven Schneider found that within an apparently-active forum discussing abortion legislation, the conversation was controlled by much-more dominant contributors, whilst spectating users typically

⁶ Fraser, Nancy. 1995. *From Redistribution to Recognition? Dilemmas of Justice in a 'Post-Socialist' Age*. New Left Review. August 1, 1995.

<https://newleftreview.org/issues/i212/articles/nancy-fraser-from-redistribution-to-recognition-dilemmas-of-justice-in-a-post-socialist-age>

⁷ NTU. 2023b. "Negative Online Reviews From Black People Perceived as Less Credible According to New Study," January 6, 2023.

<https://www.ntu.ac.uk/about-us/news/news-articles/2022/12/negative-online-reviews-from-black-people-perceived-as-less-credible-according-to-new-study?>

adjusted opinions based on shifts within these higher-contributing users⁸. These damning depictions of social exclusions and rampant discrimination propagated via inherent issues within digital technology paint an increasingly execrable issue; that digital technology degrades autonomous discussion surrounding politics as opposed to traditional discussion, worsening the people's attitudes to crucial social topics.

The propagation of inequality effectuated by digital technology within politics is not simply isolated to those who use it; its facinorous issues are also inflicted upon communities which are unable to access it, leading into global disparities between continents. The lowest internet access rates in 2023 were by increasingly underdeveloped regions within Asia/Africa at around <30%, paling in comparison to the West, which saw over 80%⁹. Given the destitution of technological infrastructure within penurious nations, many are heavily restricted from the soon-to-be \$20 trillion dollar digital economy¹⁰, accentuating an economic inability for these citizens to receive political education, or commit to partisan engagement. The paucity of technological infrastructure within underdeveloped political systems have also left

⁸ Foot, Kirsten A., and Steven M. Schneider. 2006. *Web Campaigning*. N.p.: MIT Press.

⁹ Shanahan, Matthew, Calvin Bahia, and GSMA. 2023. *The State of Mobile Internet Connectivity 2023*. GSMA.

<https://www.gsma.com/r/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/The-State-of-Mobile-Internet-Connectivity-Report-2023.pdf>

¹⁰ Delic, Kemal A., and Jeff Johnson. *The Digital Economy as a Complex System*. *Ubiquity*, vol. 2024, no. November (2024): 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3679025>

vulnerable populations at the helm of their oppressive tyrants, whereby 2023 saw governments within Sudan and Myanmar immobilising digital services, forestalling their citizens from orchestrating political revolutions^{11,12}, a blatant human-rights violation occurring thanks to advents within digital technology being tossed into corrupt hands. This disparagement is further pushed by the contrastingly innovative developments of the West¹³, allowing for highly-specific branches of politics to reign as dominant forces worldwide, reducing the diversity and culture which should, ideally, allow global politics to unite humans. Instead, digital-innovation within this field has evidently polarised us into socioeconomic groups, and has worsened our ability to coordinate as one Earth, a horrifying conclusion in-light of devastating global challenges.

¹¹ “Digital Authoritarianism in Myanmar.” n.d. University of St Andrews Research Portal.

<https://research-portal.st-andrews.ac.uk/en/activities/digital-authoritarianism-in-myanmar>

¹² Cipesa. 2023. *Sudan Conflict Affects Digital Communications and Critical Services Delivery*. Collaboration on International ICT Policy for East and Southern Africa (CIPESA). June 7, 2023.

<https://cipesa.org/2023/06/sudan-conflict-affects-digital-communications-and-critical-services-delivery/>

¹³ Heeks, Richard. (2016). *Examining 'Digital Development': The Shape of Things to Come?*. SSRN Electronic Journal. 10.2139/ssrn.3431739.

In analysing human interaction toward technology, a common, yet miscalculated belief arises, whereby modern communications allow for people to learn political systems easier, effectively constructing their own opinions, with political technology scholar Rabia Polat claiming that digitalisation leads into increasingly ‘informed societies’¹⁴. However, this assiduous trust placed within technology is dangerous, given the minute concentrations of power placed within an inexorable establishment, subliminally manipulating people’s political viewpoints on inscrutable levels.

Industry-standard forums are operated via highly-technical algorithmic data which exhibit uniquely-tailored political content, influencing billions of annual users; however, a consistent track-record of extremist political manipulation has emerged from said forums, with major sites being exposed as forcefully depicting such content onto countless individuals, fuelling misinformation, political hatred, and polarisation. A 2018 report by sociologist Zeynep Tufekci found YouTube's algorithm suggesting increasingly extremist content to users, leading into "rabbit holes" of radicalization¹⁵, with a similar 2021 study finding Twitter’s algorithms amplifying right-leaning over left-leaning politics in six of seven countries analyzed¹⁶. These unrelenting exhibitions of extremism remain both subtle to the human eye, yet

¹⁴ Polat, Rabia. (2012). *Digital exclusion in Turkey: A policy perspective*.

Government Information Quarterly. 29. 589–596. 10.1016/j.giq.2012.03.002.

¹⁵ Shaw A. *Social media, extremism, and radicalization*. Sci Adv. 2023

Sep;9(35):eadk2031. doi: 10.1126/sciadv.adk2031. Epub 2023 Aug 30. PMID: 37647405; PMCID: PMC10468141.

¹⁶ F. Huszár, S.I. Ktena, C. O’Brien, L. Belli, A. Schlaikjer, M. Hardt, *Algorithmic amplification of politics on Twitter*, Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.119 (1) e2025334119, <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2025334119> (2022).

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dangerously effective at changing one's psyche; such online radicalisation has led to real-world terror, including Capitol riots on January the 6th¹⁷, the 2024 German-market attacks¹⁸, and countless other atrocities which took-storm online. In digital communities which host majority populations of Earth, it is evident that ambiguous establishments possess unparalleled power to politically divide and promote hate on unquantifiable scales, a truly cacodemonic reality supported by digital technology, and one that is sure to irrevocably damage modern politics and the wider world going forward.

The contrast to political extremism is political indolence; a form of nonexistent, insubstantial engagement which digital technology, unsurprisingly, also stimulates. Whilst it is oftentimes claimed that technologies present potential to enliven democratic cultures with abilities to mobilise activism and movements, as seen within a 2015 MacEwan University study depicting transformative shifts within politics thanks to social-media¹⁹, the reality is much more mundane. While the

¹⁷ Boone, G. M., Taylor, M. A., & Gallant, L. (2023). *International Reactions to the Capitol Attack of January 6th: A Media Frames Analysis*. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 67(6), 784-806. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00027642221091214>

¹⁸ Connolly, Kate. 2024. "Two killed and scores injured in Germany as car ploughs into crowd at Christmas market." *The Guardian*, December 20, 2024.

<https://www.theguardian.com/world/2024/dec/20/death-and-injuries-in-germany-as-car-ploughs-into-crowd-at-christmas-market>

¹⁹ Boulianne, Shelley. 2015. *Social Media Use and Participation: A Meta-analysis of Current Research*. *Information Communication & Society* 18 (5): 524–38. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118x.2015.1008542>.

existence of digital political activism is accountable, its realistic effects are shortcoming, and its propagation of the democratic deficit is certainly much more noticeable. Initially coined by Monty Phan, a writer for Newsday in 2001²⁰, ‘Slacktivism’ characterises a nugatory contribution to politics under-the-guise of engaging in digital forms of activism, including petitions, hashtags, and more; all collectively satisfying the inner-desire to be politically active, whilst in reality achieving nothing. The ineffectiveness of such strategies are, however, blatant, as seen within a 2017 Oxford study, finding 99% of UK government-submitted petitions failing in receiving any official response²¹, or a 2023 media-technology paper proving Twitter hashtags in solidarity of current affairs to be ineffective at substantially achieving any goals²². This rise in ‘slacktivism’, however, does lead into damaging democratic deficit, whereby efforts placed into eventually-unsuccessful digital

²⁰ Clements, Warren. 2009. *A Slacktivist and His Crackberry Are Seldom Parted*. *The Globe and Mail*, May 16, 2009.

<https://www.theglobeandmail.com/arts/a-slacktivist-and-his-crackberry-are-seldom-parted/article4211196/>

²¹ Vidgen, B., Yasseri, T. *What, when and where of petitions submitted to the UK government during a time of chaos*. *Policy Sci* **53**, 535–557 (2020).

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11077-020-09395-y>

²² Highfield, T., & Miltner, K. M. (2023). *Platformed solidarity: Examining the performative politics of Twitter hashflags*. *Convergence*, 29(6), 1641-1667.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/13548565231199981>

movements divert the attention of millions away from real-world political affairs, a disproportionate distribution of attention.

And here we are again, at CERN laboratories, in the spring of 1989. As he reads through his calculations for his soon-to-be significant network, Tim-Berners Lee now unknowingly stands at the edge of two very oppositionary realities. One lies within the pre-digital era, where journalism exists to politically inform, where people can discuss albeit of rampant social exclusion, and where all countries are more united in their advancements. The post-digital reality however, is a much more dystopian one; where the power to influence billions of minds is possessed by the inscrutable few, where humans are split into classes of socioeconomic background and left to dominate over another, and where the pragmatic illusion of activism tricks countless forthcoming generations into blindly stumbling within the endless pit of political ignorance, eroding the values of democracy and politics as time goes on. Being citizens of the second reality, we're seeing evidential shifts in politics as we know it, but whether this change is positive or not, ask yourself to reflect upon this essay's question again: has digital technology really altered politics beneficially?